

Synthesis of Furano Compounds : Part-XXXIII. Synthesis of Some Pterocarpan

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Synthesis of ($\pm$)-pterocarpan, ($\pm$)-homopterocarpan and ($\pm$)-7, 8, 4'-trimethoxypterocarpan from the related chromeno (3', 4'-3, 2) coumarones are described. Two natural coumestans, e.g., trifoliol, dimethyl ether (XXIII) and 5, 6, 7'-trimethoxycoumarino (3', 4'-3, 2) coumarone, have also been synthesised.

A synthesis of 3 : 4-dihydrohomopterocarpan (I) from coumestrol dimethylether (IV) was reported earlier¹. The former has now been shown to occur naturally². It was shown that the catalytic reduction of (I) leads to hydrogenolysis giving ($\pm$)-dihydrohomopterocarpan (VIII) and homopterocarpan could not be isolated.

A few experiments have been carried out in order to obtain pterocarpan from coumestans. Thus coumestan (V) was converted into the acid (XI) which then esterified to (XII). Catalytic reduction of the furan ring of both (XI) and (XII) failed. Next, the alcohol (XIII) obtained by LAH reduction of coumestan was also found to be resistant to hydrogenation; forcing conditions led to the hydrogenolysis giving the 3-methyl derivative (XIV) characterised as its acetate. The structure of (XIV) is based on i.r. spectrum (OH absorption at 3508 cm^{-1}) and NMR spectrum (CH_3 group at $\tau 7.66$ and OH group at $\tau 3.03$ which disappears on deuteration). The catalytic reduction of coumestan with a view to reduce the 3 : 4-double bond was not possible with palladium catalyst; with Adams' catalyst the aromatic rings appear to be hydrogenated. Likewise, the hydrogenation of the derived 4-hydroxycoumarin was not feasible. However, it is now found that if (II) is catalytically hydrogenated under carefully controlled condition, a mixture of the hydrogenolysis product (IX) and ($\pm$)-pterocarpan (XVI) are obtained which are separated by fractional crystallisation. In a similar manner ($\pm$)-homopterocarpan was obtained from (I). The present synthesis is stereospecific and a different synthesis of the compound has been reported earlier⁴⁻⁶. In a similar way, a synthesis of ($\pm$)-7, 8, 4'-trimethoxypterocarpan (XVIII)^{2,3,7} was achieved by the reduction of (III), but the separation of (XVIII) from (III) was only possible by chromatography on alumina column containing silver nitrate*. The synthesis of (III) was achieved from the

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5 H. Suginome and T. Iwadare, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1966, **39**(7), 1535.

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* The reported ultra-violet and i.r. data of the synthetic compound and optically active natural compound are in agreement.

keto-nitrile (XIX) obtained by the ester condensation of methyl 2,3,4-trimethoxybenzoate and 2,4-dimethoxybenzyl cyanide. The *keto nitrile* on treatment with pyridine hydrochloride afforded the trihydroxy coumestan (VI) which was methylated to (VII), reduced with LAH to (XV) and cyclodehydrated to (III). The NMR spectrum showed three aromatic methoxyl groups at τ 6.06, 6.09 and 6.12, and methylene protons at τ 4.37.

(XXII) $R=R_{ii}=R_{iii}=OH, R_i=H.$ (XXIII) $R=R_{ii}=R_{iii}=OMe, R_i=H.$ (XXIV) $R=R_i=R_{iii}=OH, R_{ii}=H.$ (XXV) $R=R_i=R_{iii}=OMe, R_{ii}=H.$

During this work, two naturally occurring coumarino (3', 4'-3, 2) coumarones were synthesised. These are trifoliol dimethylether⁸ (XXIII) and 5, 6, 7'-trimethoxycoumarino-(3', 4'-3, 2) coumarone^{9,10} (XXV). They were secured respectively from the *keto nitriles* (XX) and (XXI) by the action of pyridine hydrochloride as described before (*vide* Experimental)

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.p.s. and b.p.s. are uncorrected. The NMR spectra are recorded in Varian A-60 apparatus using deuteriochloroform as solvent and TMS as internal standard.

2-o-Methoxyphenylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid (XI): Dimethylsulphate (1.0 ml.) was gradually added portionwise to a refluxing solution of coumestan (V; 1.0 g.) in 10% methanolic KOH in about 30 min. Refluxing was continued for further 30 min. and the mixture was acidified in the cold with hydrochloric acid. 2-o-Methoxyphenylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid (XI; 0.8 g.), separated as solid, was crystallised from acetic acid in cubes m.p. 213-5° with decomp. (Found: C, 70.98; H, 4.66. C₁₆H₁₂O₄ requires: C, 71.63; H, 4.51%).

The acid gave methyl ester (XII) with diazomethane which was distilled as thick oil at 230-40°/2mm. (bath temp.). (Found: C, 72.01; H, 5.22. C₁₇H₁₄O₄ requires: C, 72.33; H, 5.00%).

Catalytic reduction of 2-o-hydroxyphenyl-3-hydroxymethylcoumarone¹ (XIII): To a solution of (XIII; 0.2 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml.), 30% palladised charcoal (0.05 g.) was added. This suspension was subjected to hydrogenation at room temp. when hydrogen (46 ml.) was absorbed in 9 hrs. The used catalyst was removed by filtration and the crude product was dissolved in benzene and the benzene solution was passed through a column of deactivated alumina. On removal of benzene, an oily product was obtained, which was purified by distillation at 210-20° (bath temp.) and 2.5 mm. pressure. The product was found to be 2-o-hydroxyphenyl-3-methylcoumarone (XIV) (*loc. cit.*) (Found: C, 80.37; H, 5.34. C₁₅H₁₂O₂ requires: C, 80.33; H, 5.39%).

Acetyl derivative of (XIV): The phenol (XIV) was treated with acetic anhydride in dry pyridine and left overnight. On working up in the usual manner, the acetate was obtained as an oil which was distilled and crystallised from petroleum ether in prismatic needles m.p. 95-7°. (Found: C, 76.4; H, 5.1. C₁₇H₁₄O₃ requires: C, 76.67; H, 5.30%).

Chromeno(3', 4'-3,2)coumarone (II): Cyclisation of the coumarone (XIII; 1.0 g.) in boiling diethylene glycol (25 ml.) during 15 min., gave chromeno (3', 4'-3, 2)coumarone (II) which was purified by chromatography on alumina using benzene as eluent followed by crystallisation from alcohol to yield prisms (0.8 g.) m.p. 89°; (lit.¹ m.p. 89°).

(±)-*Pterocarpin (XVI)*: A mixture of absolute alcohol (30 ml.) and 10% palladised charcoal (0.075 g.) was first saturated with hydrogen at room temp. To this, chromeno (3', 4'-3,2) coumarone (0.1 g.) was added and subjected to hydrogenation. The hydrogenation was interrupted when 11.0 ml. of hydrogen was absorbed (*ca* 1/2 hour). After working

8 A. L. Livingston, E. M. Bickoff, R. E. Lundin and L. Jurd, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, **20**, 1963-70.

9 A. L. Livingston, S. C. Witt, R. E. Lundin and E. M. Bickoff, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, **30**, 2353.

10 R. R. Spencer, B. E. Knuckles and E. M. Bickoff, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**(3), 988.

up, the alkali soluble product (IX) (see below) separated and ($\pm$)-pterocarpan was isolated, which on repeated crystallisation from alcohol was obtained in prisms (70 mg.); m.p. 131-2° (lit.⁵ m.p. 126-7°); λ_{max}^{alc} 216.3 and 280.0 m μ (log ϵ , 4.2 and 3.8 respectively).

Dihydropterocarpan (IX): Chromeno (3', 4'-3, 2) coumarone (0.1 g.) was hydrogenated as above at room temp. for about 2 hrs, when the hydrogenation was complete (ca 2 moles per 1 mole of the chromen). On isolation, dihydropterocarpan crystallised from benzene-pet. ether in hard cubes, m.p. 133-4°, i.r. spectrum : 3392 cm⁻¹ (aromatic OH group). (Found : C, 79.41; H, 6.35. C₁₅H₁₄O₂ requires :C, 79.62; H, 6.24%).

($\pm$)-*Homopterocarpin (XVII)*: A mixture of absolute alcohol (30 ml.) and 10% palladised charcoal (0.075 g.) was first saturated with hydrogen at room temp. To this, 6, 7'-dimethoxychromeno (3', 4'-3, 2) coumarone¹ (I; 0.1 g.) was added and subjected to hydrogenation. When 10 ml. of hydrogen was absorbed, the hydrogenation was stopped and the product worked up to give alkali soluble dihydrohomopterocarpin, m.p. 132-3° and ($\pm$)-homopterocarpin together with some unchanged product. On repeated crystallisation from alcohol ($\pm$)-homopterocarpin was obtained as prisms (60 mg.); m.p. 131° (lit.^{5,6} 123-5° and 129-30° respectively). λ_{max}^{alc} 215 and 286.5 m μ (log ϵ , 4.37 and 3.97 respectively). The i.r. spectrum in chloroform was identical with natural (+)-homopterocarpin.

Catalytic reduction of (I) in presence of ruthenium dioxide gave the unchanged product.

α -(2,3,4-*Trimethoxybenzoyl*)-2', 4'-*dimethoxybenzyl cyanide (XIX)*: A mixture of methyl 2, 3, 4-trimethoxybenzyl cyanide (1.77 g.) in dry benzene (50 ml.) was added to dry sodium methoxide (from sodium, 0.23 g.) and refluxed for 30 hrs in an oil-bath. The product was decomposed with water, the aqueous layer was separated and washed with ether. On acidification with hydrochloric acid (1 : 1), the *keto-nitrile* (XIX) separated as an oil. It was taken up in ether, washed with NaHCO₃ soln., water and dried (MgSO₄). On evaporation the oily residue crystallised from alcohol in colourless cubes (2.2 g.), m.p. 97-8°. (Found : C, 64.74; H, 6.07. C₂₀H₂₁O₆N requires : C, 64.68; H, 5.70 %).

6, 7', 8'-*Trihydroxycoumarino* (3', 4'-3, 2) *coumarone (VI)*: The *keto-nitrile* (XIX; 1.0 g.) was heated with pyridine hydrochloride (10.0 g.) at 220-30° for 45 min. in an atmosphere of dry CO₂ with the exclusion of moisture. The melt was cooled and heated on water-bath with dil. HCl for half an hour. After cooling, the dirty clay coloured solid mass was collected. A further quantity was obtained from the liquor after extraction with ether. The whole mass was dried thoroughly in a vacuum desiccator. Yield 0.3 gm.

6, 7', 8'-*Trimethoxycoumarino* (3', 4'-3, 2) *coumarone (VII)*: The above trihydroxy compound (0.2 g.) was refluxed with dry acetone (30 ml.), anhydrous K₂CO₃ (3 g.) and methyl iodide (3 ml) for 10 hrs. The acetone solution was filtered and the solvent removed by distillation. The residue after crystallisation from acetic acid furnishes the *furo-coumarin* (VII; 0.1 g.) in light pink coloured needles, m.p. 207-8.5°. (Found : C, 65.82; H, 4.74. C₁₈H₁₄O₆ requires :C, 66.25; H, 4.32 %).

6, 7', 8'-*Triacetoxy coumarino* (3', 4'-3, 2) *coumarone (Acetyl derivative of VI)*: The foregoing trihydroxycoumarin (VI) was treated with acetic anhydride in dry pyridine and

left overnight. On working up in the usual manner, it was obtained as needles from acetic acid, m.p. 221-3°. (Found : C, 61.09; H, 3.82. $C_{21}H_{14}O_6$ requires : C, 61.47; H, 3.44 %).

2-(2'-Hydroxy-3', 4'-dimethoxyphenyl)-6-methoxy-3-hydroxymethyl-coumarone (XV) : A suspension of 6, 7', 8'-trimethoxycoumarino (3', 4'-3, 2)-coumarone (2.83 g.) in dry ether (100 ml.) containing lithium aluminium hydride (0.8 g.) was stirred for 2 hrs in the cold (15-20°) with exclusion of moisture. On working up 2-(2'-hydroxy-3', 4'-dimethoxyphenyl)-6-methoxy-3-hydroxymethylcoumarone (XV) separated from benzene as long needles (2.5 g.), m.p. 113-14°. (Found : C, 65.86, H, 5.55. $C_{18}H_{18}O_6$ requires : C, 65.44; H, 5.49%). IR spectrum : 3500 cm^{-1} (OH) and 1352 cm^{-1} (CH_2OH bending).

6, 7', 8'-Trimethoxychromeno (3', 4'-3, 2)coumarone (III) : Cyclisation of the coumarone (XV; 1.0 g.) in boiling diethylene glycol (30 ml.) for 25 min., gave 6, 7', 8'-trimethoxychromeno (3', 4'-3, 2) coumarone (III) which was purified by chromatography on alumina using benzene, followed by crystallisation from alcohol in elongated prismatic needles (0.42 g.), m.p. 135.5-136°. (Found : C, 68.95; H, 6.10. $C_{18}H_{16}O_5$ requires : C, 69.22; H, 5.16%). λ_{max}^{alc} 220.7, 246.9, 251.5, 257.0, 332.5 and 348.6 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 4.34, 4.15, 4.10, 3.98, 4.44 and 4.26 respectively), NMR spectrum (three aromatic methoxy groups at τ 6.06, 6.09 and 6.12, and methylene protons at τ 4.37).

($\pm$)-7, 8, 4'-Trimethoxypterocarpan (XVIII) : A mixture of absolute alcohol (40 ml.) and 10% palladised charcoal (0.075 g.) was first saturated with hydrogen at room temp. To this 6, 7', 8'-trimethoxychromeno (3', 4'-3, 2)-coumarone (III; 0.1 g.) was added and subjected to hydrogenation which was interrupted when 9.0 ml. of hydrogen was absorbed (ca 3/4 hour). After working up, the alkali soluble product was removed and ($\pm$)-7, 8, 4'-trimethoxypterocarpan (XVIII) was separated from unchanged chromen by passing a solution of the mixture in benzene through a silver nitrate impregnated alumina column. The compound crystallised from alcohol in prisms (0.06 g.), m.p. 117-17.5° (lit.⁷ m.p.114-5°). λ_{max}^{alc} 282 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 3.74), major i.r. peaks (KBr) 1620.4, 1612.4 and 1495.4 cm^{-1} , (lit.⁷ λ_{max}^{MeOH} 283 (log ϵ , 3.83) and 290 (inf.) $m\mu$ and major i.r. peaks (KBr) at 1620, 1615 and 1500 cm^{-1}).

2, 4, 6-Trimethoxybenzyl cyanide : The cyanide was prepared according to Whalley¹¹ with the following modification. The mixture of 2, 4, 6-trimethoxyphenylpyruvic acid and benzoic acid was treated with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and the resulting mixture of the oxime and benzoic acid was treated with acetic anhydride on water bath for ten minutes. On working up the cyanide was obtained, yield 50% of the theoretical, m.p. 115.5-16° (lit.¹¹ m.p. 117°).

α -(2, 4-Dimethoxybenzoyl)2', 4', 6'-trimethoxybenzyl cyanide (XX) : Condensation of ethyl 2, 4-dimethoxybenzoate (2.2 g.) with 2, 4, 6-trimethoxybenzyl cyanide (2.07 g.) in refluxing dry benzene (50 ml.) was carried out in presence of sodium hydride (0.8 g., 50% in oil) for 90 hrs. On working up as before (*vide* prepn. of XIX), the keto-nitrile (XX) was obtained as shining colourless cubes (2.7 g.), m.p. 133-4°. (Found : C, 64.74; H, 5.93; N, 3.93. $C_{20}H_{21}O_6N$ requires : C, 64.68; H, 5.70; N, 3.77%); IR spectrum : 1682 cm^{-1} (carbonyl) and 2242 cm^{-1} (nitrile).

4, 6, 7'-*Trihydroxycoumarino*(3', 4'-3, 2) *coumarone* (XXII) (*Demethyltrifolol*): The *keto-nitrile* (XX; 1.0 g.) was heated with pyridine hydrochloride (10 g.) at 220-30° for 45 min. in an atmosphere of dry CO₂ with exclusion of moisture. The melt was cooled and heated over water bath with dil. HCl for half an hour. After cooling, the brown solid (XXII; 0.7 g.) was separated and dried, m.p. above 300°; (lit.⁸ m.p. 346-8°).

4, 6, 7'-*Trimethoxycoumarino* (3', 4'-3, 2) *coumarone* (XXIII) (*Trifolol dimethylether*): Methylation of the above trihydroxy compound (XXII; 0.2 g.) in dry acetone (20 ml.) was carried out as before (*cf.* prepn. of VII), using anhydrous K₂CO₃ (3 g.) and methyl iodide (3 ml.) to give, after the usual work up, the product (XXIII; 120 mg.), crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 255-7°, (lit.⁸ m.p. 255-8°); (Found: C, 65.87; H, 4.77. C₁₈H₁₄O₆ requires: C, 66.25, H, 4.32%); IR spectrum: 1731 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl). It was found identical with the natural authentic sample (mixed m.p. and superimposable i.r. spectrum).

4, 6, 7'-*Triacetoxycoumarino*(3', 4'-3, 2) *coumarone* (*Acetyl derivative of XXII*) The trihydroxycoumestan (XXII) was treated with acetic anhydride in dry pyridine and left overnight. On working up in the usual manner, it was obtained as soft needles from acetic acid, m.p. 209-11° (lit.⁸ m.p. 212°); (Found: C, 61.81; H, 3.80. C₂₁H₁₄O₉ requires: C, 61.47; H, 3.44%). IR spectrum: 1745 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl).

α -(2, 4-*Dimethoxybenzoyl*)-2', 4', 5'-*trimethoxybenzyl cyanide* (XXI): Condensation of ethyl 2,4-dimethoxybenzoate (2.2 g.) with 2, 4, 5-trimethoxybenzyl cyanide (2.07 g.) in refluxing dry benzene (50 ml.) was carried out in presence of sodium hydride (0.8 g., 50% in oil) for 36 hrs. On working up as before (*vide* prepn. of XIX), the *keto-nitrile* (XXI) was obtained as shining colourless cubes (2.3 g.), m.p. 107-9°; (Found: C, 64.25; H, 5.2; N, 3.88. C₂₀H₂₁O₆N requires: C, 64.68; H, 5.7; N, 3.77%). IR spectrum: 1664 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl), and 2249 cm⁻¹ (nitrile).

5, 6, 7'-*Trihydroxycoumarino*(3', 4'-3, 2) *coumarone* (XXIV): The *keto-nitrile* (XXI; 2 g.) was heated with pyridine hydrochloride (20 g.) at 220-30° for 45 min. in an atmosphere of dry CO₂ with exclusion of moisture. The melt was cooled and heated over water bath with dil. hydrochloric acid for half an hour. After cooling the dirty white solid (1.5 g.) was collected, m.p. above 300°.

5, 6, 7'-*Trimethoxycoumarino* (3', 4'-3, 2) *coumarone* (XXV): Methylation of the above trihydroxy compound (XXIV; 0.2 g.) in dry acetone (20 ml.) was carried out as before (*cf.* prepn. of VII), using anhydrous K₂CO₃ (3 g.) and methyl iodide (3 ml.) to give, after the usual work up, the product (XXV), crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 250-2°, (lit.⁹ m.p. 254°); (Found: C, 65.86; H, 4.80. C₁₈H₁₄O₆ requires: C, 66.25; H, 4.32%).

5, 6, 7'-*Triacetoxycoumarino* (3', 4'-3, 2) *coumarone* (*Acetyl derivative of XXIV*): The trihydroxycoumestan (XXIV) was treated with acetic anhydride in dry pyridine and left overnight. On working up in the usual manner, the acetyl derivative crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 258-60°, (lit.⁹ m.p. 255-7°); (Found: C, 62.07; H, 4.05. C₂₁H₁₄O₉ requires: C, 61.47; H, 3.44%).

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